

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL MWNT SHEET/EPOXY COMPOSITES

N. Morisawa^{1*}, Y. Shimamura², K. Tohgo², T. Fujii², Y. Inoue³

¹Graduate student of Shizuoka University, Japan,

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Shizuoka University, Japan,

³Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Shizuoka University, Japan

(*Corresponding Author: nmorisawa@mechamat.eng.shizuoka.ac.jp)

Keywords: Carbon nanotube, Unidirectional MWNT sheet, CNT composite, Mechanical property

1. Introduction

Carbon fibers, which have high specific strength and stiffness, are the main stream of reinforcement of composites used for light-weight structural components. Carbon nanotubes (CNT) are expected to exceed the mechanical properties of carbon fibers. Recently, unidirectional MWNT sheets have been developed by Inoue et al. [1,2]. In this study, thermoset composites are made by using the unidirectional MWNT sheets, and then tensile tests were conducted to investigate the mechanical properties. The fracture mechanism was discussed using SEM observation of fracture surface.

2. Materials

Multi walled carbon nanotube (MWNT) were prepared by Inoue et al [1]. MWNTs were grown on a quartz glass plate with chemical vapor deposition (CM-CVD method), and drawn into sheets by pulling out. MWNTs were contracted by Van der Waals' force during drawing process. Figure 1 shows a schematic of drawing MWNT sheets and Fig.2 shows a SEM image of MWNT sheet. The length and diameter of MWNT were 1.2mm and 50 μ m, respectively. The thickness of MWNT sheet was about 16 μ m and the specific density was 0.4. Two types of bisphenol-A type epoxy were used for the matrix. One was room-temperature cure epoxy and the other was high-temperature cure epoxy (150°C \times 3hr)

Fig.1 Schematic of drawing MWNT sheet.

Fig.2 SEM image of MWNT sheet.

3. Specimens and experimental method.

The hand lay-up method was used to fabricate composites. After curing, the thin composite plate was cut into rectangular specimens. Fiber volume contents of composites were measured by using thermo gravimetric analysis. Specimens for tensile tests were prepared as shown in Fig.3. The both ends of a composite specimen were glued onto a paper mount. The paper mount was cut before tensile testing. The cross-head speed was 1mm/min. Displacement was measured by using a noncontact extensometer.

Fig.3 Specimen configuration.

4. Composite using room-temperature cure epoxy

Epoxy resin with room-temperature curing was used for matrix. Fiber volume fractions of composite were 4.1% and 7.8%, respectively. Figure 4 shows stress-strain curves of MWNT sheet, resin and composites. Figure 5 shows SEM images of the top view of the fracture portion and Fig.6 shows SEM images of fracture surface of composite specimens.

Fig.4 Stress-strain curves.

(a) $V_f = 4.1\%$

(b) $V_f = 7.8\%$

Fig.5 SEM image of fracture portion

(a) $V_f = 4.1\%$

(b) $V_f = 7.8\%$

Fig.6 SEM image of fracture surface.

Fig.7 SEM image of cutting surface.

Young's modulus increased from 2.9GPa for pure epoxy to 20.0GPa for a composite with $V_f=4.1\%$ and to 13.4GPa for a composite with $V_f=7.8\%$, respectively. Tensile strength increased from 61.0MPa for pure epoxy to 64.4MPa for a composite with $V_f=4.1\%$ and to 78.2MPa for a composite with $V_f=7.8\%$, respectively. The improvement of tensile strength was not significant compared with that of Young's modulus. The high Young's modulus and tensile strength probably achieved because of high load transfer from resin to MWNTs as a result of using longer nanotubes. Many pull-outs of MWNTs about 10 μm were found, and this would bring the less enhancement of tensile strength. In spite of increasing fiber volume content, the composite with $V_f=7.8\%$ showed lower Young's modulus than that of composite with $V_f=4.1\%$. Figure 7 shows a SEM image of cutting surface. The imperfect impregnation might be the reason for the lower Young's modulus.

5. Composite using high-temperature cure epoxy

The improvement of tensile strength was not high when room-temperature cure epoxy was used. Many pull-outs of MWNTs suggested that the bonding force between MWNT and resin be insufficient, and the load transmitting be not made enough. Then, in order to enhance the friction force between MWNT and resin, epoxy resin of high-temperature cure was used for matrix. Fiber volume fractions of composites were 6.4% and 13.7%, respectively. Figure 8 shows stress-strain curves of MWNT sheet, resin and composites. Figure 9 shows SEM images of the top view of the fracture portion and Fig.10 shows SEM images of the fracture surface of composite specimens.

Young's modulus increased from 2.6GPa for pure epoxy to 13.4GPa for a composite with $V_f=4.1\%$ and to 44.7GPa for a composite with $V_f=7.8\%$, respectively. Tensile strength increased from 81.2MPa for pure epoxy to 123.8MPa for a composite with $V_f=4.1\%$ and to 166.2MPa for a composite with $V_f=7.8\%$, respectively. Many pull-outs of MWNTs about 10 μm were found as for room-temperature cure epoxy. Figure 11 and 12 show Young's modulus and tensile strength as a function of the volume fraction.

Fig.8 Stress-strain curves

(a) $V_f=5.0\%$

(a) $V_f=13.7\%$

Fig.9 SEM image of fracture portion

(a) $V_f = 5.0\%$

(a) $V_f = 13.7\%$

Fig.10 SEM image of fracture surface

Fig.12 Tensile strength vs. V_f

When the fiber volume fraction was less than 5%, the Young's modulus was relatively close to the predictions by the Cox theory. When the fiber volume fraction was larger than 5%, the Young's modulus was much smaller than the estimates by the Cox theory. This is properly because of the imperfect impregnation of resin.

Large influence on the tensile strength was seen by changing the types of resin. Composites using high-temperature cure epoxy showed higher tensile strengths than those of room temperature cure epoxy. The higher tensile strength was probably obtained due to increase of the frictional force between MWNT and resin as a result of higher thermal contraction of high-temperature cure epoxy.

6. Conclusions

In this study, unidirectional MWNT sheet reinforced epoxy composites were fabricated and tensile tests were conducted. Both Young's modulus and tensile strength could be improved by using the unidirectional MWNT sheet.

References

- [1] Y.Inoue, K.Kakihata, Y.Hirono, T.Horie, A. Ishida, and H.Mimura "One-step grown aligned bulk carbon nanotubes by chloride mediated chemical vapor

Fig.11 Young's modulus vs. V_f

deposition". *APPLIED PHYSICS LETTERS*, 92, 213113, 2008

- [2] Y.Inoue, Y.Suzuki, Y.Minami, J.Muramatsu, Y.Shimamura, K.Suzuki, A.Ghemes, M.Okada, S.Sakakibara, H.Mimura, K.Naito "Anisotropic carbon nanotube papers fabricated from multiwalled carbon nanotube webs". *Carbon*, Volume 49, Issue 7, June 2011, Pages 2437-2443